

Boosting European Citizens' Knowledge and Awareness
of Bio-Economy Research and Innovation

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Policy Brief on the Concept of public engagement in bioeconomy

Report

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Responsible Organisation	Wissenschaftsladen Bonn
Author(s)	N. Steinhaus
Reviewers	R. Kranendonk, J. Feichtinger

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Executive Summary

BLOOM is an EU Coordination and Support Action in the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme and was implemented from 2017 to 2020. The project aimed at bringing together partners from across Europe to debate, communicate, and engage the public in exploring the potential of bioeconomy.

BLOOM stands for “Boosting European citizens’ knowledge and awareness of bioeconomy research and innovation”. The project aims at boosting European citizens’ knowledge and awareness of bioeconomy research and innovation and was dedicated to setting up five national hubs that served as platforms where bioeconomy stakeholders can be engaged to help increase public awareness and seek out opportunities for the bioeconomy.

This report is based on results, findings, comments and recommendations which continuously were reported in BLOOM’s deliverables throughout the project period, starting from the Bioeconomy Mapping Report and the Communication Framework and including the Final Report on Hub Activities.

It starts with a brief overview of the bioeconomy background the hubs are working against, highlighting that it is essential that engagement processes are embedded within current and future innovation pathways to further develop Europe’s economy in a social and environmental responsible manner.

The second chapter will describe BLOOM’s specific approach, which addresses regional innovation, smart specialization, quadruple helix interplay and relies on the process requirements of Diversity and Inclusion, Openness and Transparency, Anticipation and Reflection and Responsiveness and Adaptive Change set out in the RRI-Tools project. A specific focus is set on engagement as core element of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). BLOOM’s target audiences, the project’s communication concept and the process of developing bioeconomy key messages to be used in the activities is described. Results from interviews with practitioners from each hub region add to the global picture of awareness problems regarding the concepts and needed dialogue formats in bioeconomy.

The third chapter describes in brief the challenges on awareness raising, network extension and education and training the hubs identified during the implementation of the co-creation and outreach activities, such as narrow ranges of interest, lack of communication, or lack of knowledge about the potential of biobased products.

Chapter four outlines the BLOOM Hub-learnings when conveying the concept of bioeconomy. Learning on co-creation and learnings on implementing co-created outreach activities are described, highlighting that the co-creation allowed a lot of stakeholders from different sectors of society to get together for the first time and to understand the importance of communication and of citizen involvement for the transition and implementation of bioeconomy.

Based on these experiences chapter five dares a look into the future and gives recommendations on communication and outreach and co-creation, such as to empower scientists so that they can communicate scientific, policy and business knowledge, on education, such as including the topic in classrooms with actions that support the current curricula, on governance, such as fostering the region approach and interregional exchange and for business and industry, such as to open up

their view on new concepts and ideas, hopefully to be considered when getting into further collaborative actions in a multiple-stakeholder approach.

The last chapter shares some final experiences and recommendations from each BLOOM hub.

1. Background

“The bioeconomy encompasses the production of renewable biological resources and the conversion of these resources, residues, by-products and side streams into value added products, such as food, feed, bio-based products, services and bioenergy.” [1]

The Europe 2020 Strategy called for a bioeconomy as a key element for smart and green growth in Europe with clear regional approaches. Raising awareness for the advancements in bioeconomy research and innovation will allow Europe to improve the management of natural resources and to open new and diversified markets in food and bio-based products.

The participants of a high level Bioeconomy Policy event, organized by the European Commission in November 2016 the European Commission to discuss the progress on the delivery of the European Union’s Bioeconomy Strategy and Action Plan summarized: “A sustainable, circular bioeconomy has the potential to reconcile human needs with nature, in the context of Sustainable Development Goals, and to ease the transition to a post-fossil-fuel future. The bioeconomy is cross-sectoral and vast, encompassing all regions of Europe, from traditional activities, such as cork harvesting, to cutting-edge technology.” [2]

The rapporteurs of the above mentioned high level Bioeconomy policy event [2] continued that bioeconomy is often misunderstood because of its diverse nature and that actors in the bioeconomy may not even be aware of their contribution to the whole bioeconomy because they consider themselves as part of only one sub-sector. The event report therefore concludes that bioeconomy requires education, changes in public perception and research.

A couple of barriers are reported for different bioeconomic sectors. Priefer, Jörissen and Frör stated 2017 that “besides the current European framework conditions, there are a number of barriers that hinder the implementation of the cascading approach (in waste hierarchy and changing biomass into biogenic products). This includes logistic and financial restrictions, the lack of economic incentives for the use of secondary materials, and a lack of information and awareness about resource scarcity among consumers.” [4]

In November 2017 the Bioeconomy Stakeholder Panel published a Manifesto and indicated guiding principles, actions and recommendations for further deployment of bioeconomy in Europe.

The following proposed guiding principles and actions were central part of the BLOOM project:

Cooperation between sectors and actors along and across value-chains: “This (principle) requires efforts to bring actors together and a holistic approach that is respectful to the varying situation for stakeholders from different parts of the bioeconomy-web. By giving more visibility among sectors and to consumers, the innovations will diversify and market pull can be stimulated for new products...” [3]

Importance of regional strategies and rural renaissance: Regions are key actors in developing the European bioeconomy and a strong bioeconomy can make regions more economically attractive. ... The bioeconomy can help Europe revitalise rural areas. A European bioeconomy will offer a new perspective on traditional and high-value production in the regions, as well as creating new opportunities and jobs for farming, forestry, fisheries, aquaculture and industry. [3]

Actions

Enhancing education, training and skills. Education of school children and high school students are crucial to raise a generation that can understand the challenges and embrace the opportunities of a bioeconomy. For example, teaching principles of circularity, of acting global and local at the same time (glocal), and raising interest for exploration will contribute to preparing the new generation to find its way...

Raising public awareness is essential in order to ensure the development of a smart, sustainable and inclusive bioeconomy, to create a market for sustainable bio-based products and to promote more sustainable consumption and lifestyle patterns. [3]”

Raising awareness for new economic processes requires the support and active contribution of many different actors along value chains and their socio-political context. It is therefore necessary when promoting bio-based and circular economy, both the general public (citizens and end-users) and key stakeholders (policy-makers, scientists, non-governmental organisations, civil society organisations, entrepreneurs, etc.) have to be involved in an open and informed dialogue. The engagement of actors involved in regional or national strategies needs to be recognized, as national strategies are closely related to economic policy-making, while regional strategies may be developed by economic clusters and shaped by discrete groups of actors and networks in a specific region, often in less formal ways.

BLOOM’s Bioeconomy Mapping Report (deliverable 1.1) describes the framework in which the European bioeconomy is set up, which include a technical overview, possible frameworks for transition and international and national policies of relevance for the bioeconomy.

2. The BLOOM approach

BLOOM stands for “Boosting European citizens’ knowledge and awareness of bioeconomy research and innovation”. BLOOM will address three aspects related to the transition to a European bioeconomy: awareness raising, education/ training and stakeholder network extension.

BLOOM’s approaches and activities were applied in five regional hubs, which have selected bioeconomy as smart specialization strategy. In this aspect, the project pursued to strengthen the dialogue on practical opportunities in areas or sectors that are important for the region, and to demonstrate the specific, regional benefits while engaging with stakeholders. BLOOM’s interactions therefore and in this context aimed to

- (a) raise awareness and knowledge on bioeconomy by enabling open and informed dialogue throughout the bioeconomy innovation processes
- (b) build up and strengthen a bioeconomy community and extend the triple helix of actors to a quadruple helix by engaging the civil society (organizations),
- (c) gain a common understanding of the concept, providing reliable insights into bioeconomies, its practices, benefits and implications
- (d) foster learning and education.

With that, the project supported the reduction of barriers towards a bioeconomy identified in stakeholder dialogues and stimulated bioeconomy activities at the regional and EU level.

In the regional hubs triple helix partners already work on innovation pipelines, from new ideas to valorise regional biomass to biobased products, to the implementation of new bioeconomy practices. BLOOM will support these partner's activities with a focus on raising awareness, fostering bioeconomic understanding and extending the current networks especially with civil society.

Regional and local stakeholder engagement is important for the co-creation of a responsible bioeconomy, to be well understood by and beneficial to all citizens (EU Bioeconomy Investment summit 2015). For the engagement of stakeholder groups, it is therefore crucial that the diversity of values, types of knowledge, types of voices and demographics are appropriate.

Mutual learning and (new) transdisciplinary skills and competence are necessary, specifically with regard to successful new business models, suitable policy practices and sustainability standards (TOBE, 2014).

Education, training, communication and outreach are crucial for a future bioeconomy. To achieve this, one has to start with promotion and accessibility of existing knowledge (potential, perspectives and products) and to invest in the transfer of knowledge (open access, open innovation, open science). For this reason, BLOOM's approach supported and facilitated a strong interconnection and an open dialog among education providers, producers, citizens, researchers and innovators when working together.

As BLOOM's main objective was to establish open and informed dialogues, co-created by European citizens, the civil society, bioeconomy innovation networks, local research centres, business and industry stakeholders and various levels of government, the project's guiding principles and actions focused on raising awareness and understanding (of citizens and the young generation), and on collaboration and exchange between various partners (along the value chain, in regions, different perspectives).

2.1. Stakeholder Engagement in the context of RRI¹

The selection of stakeholders strongly influences the outcomes of engagement. It thus needs an effective representation of stakeholders including those who are highly interests even with low power and strategic stakeholders with high influence, power and means.

BLOOM focused on involvement and engagement of all stakeholders, getting to know each other, enabling cross-fertilization and idea generation through shared knowledge and experiences. BLOOM designed and facilitated the co-creation of outreach activities that were exactly adapted to the regional needs of the stakeholders. Details can be found in the stakeholder mapping report (Deliverable 3.1)

¹https://www.rri-tools.eu/documents/10184/107098/D1.3_QualityCriteriaGoodPracticeStandards.pdf/ca4efe26-6fb2-4990-8dde-fe3b4aed1676

Figure 1: Stakeholder engagement criteria

Table 1 Stakeholder Engagement Criteria and Specifications

Criteria	Specification	
	<i>Indicators/sub-criteria</i>	<i>Questions that invite thinking about indicators and criteria</i>
Engaging a variety of stakeholder groups	Wide range	Is there a wide range of stakeholders involved, such that there is a diversity of values and a diversity of types of knowledge/expertise (i.e., experiential knowledge, scientific knowledge) represented and/or generated? (Rowe and Frewer, 2000)
	Relevant voices	Is there diversity in the stakeholders engaged such that all relevant voices are heard – silent as well as loud (i.e., stakeholder groups that might not feel immediately empowered to let their view know and stakeholder groups that do)?
	Demographic diversity	Is there diversity within the stakeholder groups involved in terms of gender, ethnicity, class, age and other demographics?
	Sufficient amount	Are sufficiently many perspectives and participants included, such that eventual outcomes are robust? (ScienceWise, 2013)
Variety of means of stakeholder engagement	Early involvement	Are relevant stakeholders involved from early stages of the R&I trajectory onwards?
	Engagement methods	Are different methods and techniques for engaging specific stakeholder groups in dialogue taken into consideration? (e.g., is terminology ad-

		<i>justed to interlocutors; is the method for deliberation - interviews, focus groups etc.- tailored to the target stakeholder?)</i>
	Commitment	<i>Are all stakeholders committed to the practice throughout all stages of the R&I trajectory and do they feel empowered to challenge directions of research and innovation?</i>
Engagement of public(s)	Facilitating deliberation	<i>Are there (new) deliberative forums on issues involving science and innovation, moving beyond engagement with stakeholders to include members of the wider public? (Stilgoe et al., 2013)</i>
	Pertinent engagement	<i>Are the right publics involved in the right phases of the R&I trajectory?</i>
	Development of capabilities	<i>Are different possibilities explored or activities undertaken to facilitate the development of capabilities of publics to contribute to a science-literate society (i.e., become scientific citizens)?</i>
Institutional diversity	Internal social differences	<i>Is there attention and respect for group/social differences within the R&I practice (e.g., gender, race/ethnicity, class, sexual orientation, country of origin, and ability as well as cultural, political, religious, or other affiliations)?</i>
	Minority recruitment strategies	<i>Are there minority recruitment strategies in place to increase, within the practice itself, a balance in race/ethnicity, class, gender, sexual orientation, country of origin, and ability, as well as cultural, political, religious, or other affiliations?</i>
Attention for appropriate R&I models and methods	Diversity of methods	<i>Are methods for research and innovation being developed or discussed with different stakeholders such that they respond to the needs and expectations of the different stakeholders? (i.e., considering a wide range of methods and employing an inter- or transdisciplinary process) (Wickson and Carew, 2014)</i>
	Research objects	<i>Is there diversity within the objects of research, in terms of gender and other demographics? (e.g., are not only male animal models used?)</i>
Flexible attitudes to revise views and actions	Individuals	<i>Are the individuals involved willing and able to revise their views and actions?</i>
	Organizations	<i>Do the organizations involved offer adaptive space to respond flexibly to changing circumstances, changing needs and values of other stakeholders and organizations involved? (e.g., are research organizations open to rewarding their staff for non-scientific output, such as popular media appearances?)</i>
Changing responsibilities	Role responsibilities	<i>Are actors involved prepared to take, enlarge and/or redefine their role responsibilities? (Stilgoe et al., 2013)</i>
	Acceptance of accountability	<i>Are actors prepared to accept, through processes of dialogue, accountability fitting their role for potential positive and negative impacts, choices and processes? (Wickson and Carew, 2014)</i>
Application of results	Stakeholders	<i>Are (affected) stakeholders willing and equipped to apply new knowledge, values/norms and competencies? (e.g., the use of results of a research practice for educational purposes)</i>
	Organizations and systems	<i>Do the organizations and systems involved offer adaptive space to respond flexibly to changing knowledge, values/norms and learned competencies?</i>

Figure 2: RRI-Tool quality criteria catalogue 'Stakeholder engagement'

2.2. BLOOM's Communication concept

As outlined before, there is a growing need for information, advice and guidance, from increasing capacity to improved integration of co-created outreach activities.

BLOOM aimed at initiating structured and consistent communication on bioeconomy innovation processes and the state of the art of the bioeconomy research across a range of on- and offline platforms, tools and methods with a view to boosting knowledge of the general European public (See D6.1).

Thus, effective, integrated and coordinated communication was integral to carrying out BLOOM's activities for raising awareness and increased networking on bio-based economy issues. BLOOM's communication approach was presented as a framework of principles for effective practice that apply to a broad range of communications functions. Measures were included to develop communication products and activities (see D6.1). The hub coordinators followed the guidance given in deliverables 3.1, 3.3 and 6.1.

By stakeholders contributing to the concept, the design and the performance of the outreach events, they became 'owners' of activities and results, tasked with promoting the results and contributing to bioeconomy in the long run as 'ambassadors' or multipliers.

Each regional hub organised several open dialog events in different forms to allow for the involvement of different persons and groups. The hubs also developed services to society and identi-

fied ‘multipliers’ for communication that carried the message even beyond the regional networks. By identifying major facilitators and barriers in the co-creation workshops addressed and advanced understanding of the steps to take to accelerate the bio-economy deployment.

2.3. Target Audiences

Within regions, triple helix organizations have already collaboratively set common smart specialization strategies. The focus of BLOOM’s activities therefore laid on reaching out for more people and organizations, to participate, support and act in the direction of a broader awareness of benefits and opportunities of a bio-based economy and followed a quadruple helix model of innovation that extended the current collaboration between government, industry, academia with Civil Society as the sector of voluntary action within institutional forms that are distinct from those of the state, family and market, consists of a large and diverse set of voluntary organizations, often competing with each other and oriented to specific interests. The quadruple helix model for innovation brings these multidisciplinary viewpoints together in an environment that promotes team working, collaboration and the sharing of ideas.

BLOOM target audiences included the general public, NGOs, the media and identified regional, national and international bioeconomy communities, like bio-based industries, bioeconomy stakeholder panel, EU institutes, bio-based regions and regional networks. But BLOOM also targeted on specific bioeconomy projects, events, platforms (that are focusing on bioeconomy for specific target groups like industry or strategy platforms) and the participation of e.g. young European citizens and educational institutes and science communication networks.

Involving the general public together with the other above mentioned in bioeconomy research and innovation and awareness raising agendas required designing arenas for co-creation and innovation. BLOOM worked hub-centred in multi-stakeholder engagement processes to co-create activities which fostered knowledge, exchange, learning, engagement and connections between all actors and actor groups.

2.4. Key messages

The development of the bioeconomy needs to be driven by the desire to meet several of the big societal challenges of our time. [2]

BLOOM's developed outreach activities were based on EU research and innovation, mapped in the Bioeconomy Mapping Report (Deliverable D1.1). The challenge of communicating these often complex and inter-linked issues of a bio-based economy were tackled by framing information within the context of overarching key narratives:

- **The environment and climate are at the core of all societal and economic issues.** We all rely on resources or services provided by the natural world. By integrating environmental and climate concerns into a wider range of areas of policy, it is possible to find solutions that are economically, socially and environmentally sustainable.

- **There is an urgent need to improve ecological resilience.** Many aspects of the natural world are now changing at a faster rate than modern society has ever experienced. We must ensure that actions avoid lock-in into unsustainable systems of consumption and production and instead open pathways to the sustainable use of resources and ecosystem services.
- **To introduce and implement biobased economy's innovations, a society-wide increase of awareness of opportunities is needed.** Access to information, communications and informative events about the bioeconomy (events, public discussions, discussions in the media etc.) and its products as well as the involvement of civil society and other stakeholders in decision-making processes (public consultations etc) are needed to enable society to follow on-going developments in industry and research.
- **Closing the information and knowledge gap between stakeholders.** Research and the application of its results are often disconnected due to information and knowledge gaps and institutional and conceptual barriers between researchers, innovators, industry, educational institutes, policy-makers and the civil society. Knowledge transfer has to be facilitated through co-creation with and for stakeholders.
- **Improving the biobased economy requires better implementation of policies and strategies.** To meet this goal, it is needed to gain better knowledge on the state of the innovation, measures taken and the expected effects of policies. An important aspect was to connect triple helix activities as strategies and dynamics with civil society in regions. From a transition perspective society has still been missing and is needed for a full implementation and upscaling.
- **Innovations are achieved at local, regional and global levels.** Through creativity, networking and action, local and regional frontrunners can improve quality of life and help implementing bioeconomic innovations, processes and products. At the same time, governments and the international community need to step up their commitment and efforts in improving a bio-based economy by making the next step from triple to quadruple helix and to apply new insights together with all actors.

These broad narratives were specified at the level of individual, hub-related, bio-economic themes and outputs. Targeted output on mind – a series of collaborative and engaging outreach activities covering awareness, education and network extension -different innovative outreach formats were suggested.

2.5. Interviews to get practitioners' views on co-creation and outreach

To identify best practice examples of communication strategies of different target audiences, including the identification of barriers, drivers and its implementation, a set of five stakeholder interviews was conducted in the different hubs. BLOOM partners were asked to provide names of interviewees from their hub. The purpose of the interviews was to get input from selected stakeholders on experiences with outreach materials and communication activities related to bioecon-

omy and shall add to the global picture of awareness problems regarding the concepts and needed dialogue formats in bioeconomy.

The interviews have been conducted by phone with interviewees from Austria, Spain, the Netherlands, Finland and Poland between January and May 2020 with two policy makers from national ministries, two researchers and one teacher from a vocational education institute. One interviewee answered the questions in writing.

All Interviewees were experienced in BE topics on different levels with research addressing both academia and companies, practical exercises with and for students, which are not directly linked to bioeconomy but address BE issues on a broader level such as waste management or bio waste or as policy offers in ministries working on interdepartmental programs or the development of the national bioeconomy strategy.

Their answers therefore didn't build any empirical basis but put a spotlight on bioeconomy across different stakeholder groups across Europe.

The interviews assessed existing collaboration (options) with BLOOM, and helped to identify additional valuable insights for the development of outreach activities and the production of information material to be promoted through BLOOM.

The questions asked addressed the awareness for bioeconomy in general, and national and regional strategies for Bioeconomy, took a look into the future and explored networking opportunities.

The challenges reported by the interviewees are summarised and integrated in the following chapters, keeping on mind that there was just one interviewee per hub and the interviews as such only were meant to get a better grip on the addressed issues.

3. Identified Challenges

Besides addressing the fact that among civil society there is only little knowledge about bio-based economy and low excitement, because of a lack of current context, a specific challenge addressed by BLOOM was to foster involvement and regular dialogue during the different stages of the innovation process in order to build strong involvement for meaningful co-innovation.

Another obstacle was the fact that education in general is often disconnected from scientific, societal or innovation issues and challenges. This doesn't mean that there is no exchange between education and e.g. private sector initiatives, but these approaches need to be better structurally incorporated. Approaches to change from a subject orientated teaching to interdisciplinary or even transdisciplinary learning are rather slow and hardly implemented in Europe. At the level of universities and higher education institutes, educational programmes, courses, departments dealing with the bioeconomy are gradually being developed. Yet, the Bioeconomy in school education needs more attention.

Targeting awareness

A low awareness of the potential of the bioeconomy and the conditions for realising the bioeconomy was identified as the central challenge in the hub activities. Awareness, knowledge and

commitment needed to be created, tailored with and for the different target groups by applying a co-creation approach on different interactive events in public space and convergence of media channels.

Targeting Education and Training

Circular Sustainable Bioeconomy is not part of the curriculum yet, lectures are determined by the curriculum, so far CBS is only taken up in teaching as “extra” to the curriculum.

Teacher trainings thus represent an important and strategic component for the dissemination and uptake of innovative STEM practices, and for the BLOOM project in particular, the uptake of bio economy by young citizens. To address teachers as an indispensable medium for transmitting the applications of bio economy in education at local level, existing educational tools had to be collected and structured:

- Identifying target groups: to describe the target groups of users that will be chosen and addressed for the collection of the material to be further developed into the educational tools
- Identifying contents and source of material: selecting the topics and issues related to bio-based products and the bio-based economy for which material has to be collected (described in D1.3)
- Identifying educational tools: to briefly outline the tools that have already been developed and explore what is planned for the future

BLOOM provided teachers with a set of bioeconomy educational resources that cover a variety of subjects, from food production to chemistry – The BLOOM School Box (Deliverable D4.1), accompanied by a teachers training organisational framework (Deliverable D4.2). These resources address different students, depending on their background and experiences thus providing teachers with points of references and possibilities to open dialogues within diverse classrooms and bridge possible social gaps. BLOOM also ensured that teachers were either trained or had access to local support that will help them implement them. Through BLOOM’s teacher trainings, the number of teachers who will use bio economy in their lessons increased.

Targeting network extension

Through its Hubs BLOOM sought collaboration with regional Bio Economy Networks, local partners in the education sector, training institutions, stakeholders that work on policy formulation as well as industry experts and as such expanded existing networks. BLOOM also linked with ongoing and finished bioeconomy projects and their project partners through contributing to their previously established platforms as well as through inviting project key persons to workshops and events to share previous experiences on education and training or communication and outreach.

3.1. The Hub findings on challenges in brief

Explanatory comments on concerns, barriers, needs and strategies in this chapter are based on desktop research and the interviews as well as on results of implemented co-creation workshops. Details are given in Deliverable D3.2 “Roadmap and Synthesis of hubs”.

The identified experiences on starting conditions were quite different in the hubs. While the impression from the Netherlands’ interviewee was that of low interest in new ideas and innovations as the position of the ministry is giving food a more important focus than growing biomass for non-food applications, the interviewee and partners from Spain were excited about the openness for new concepts and new ideas of solving problems. The concern of e.g. of farmers regarding climate change was very high, also their fear that consumers might decide against their products if environmental aspects are not considered. The feedback on the Austrian bioeconomy strategy was consistently positive - both at national and international level. In particular, the area of “sustainable consumption” was received positively among stakeholders. The Finnish interviewee e.g. recognised a growing conflict between economic and biodiversity/ecosystem issues with not enough knowledge about the different perspectives of stakeholders but also mentioned a raising awareness on how to use resources and a positive connotation of the term bioeconomy. In general bioeconomy is perceived as a future issue and is also seen as an approach to dealing e.g. with the consequences of climate change. Challenges reported by the interviewees were:

- In certain settings is not much interest in new ideas and innovations.
- It is hard to convince companies to change their production line, large companies are not prepared to transform, they communicate only on small interventions.
- Prices for products are too high and there is a huge lack of knowledge about the potential of bio-based products.
- There was much interaction in the beginning of the bioeconomy discourse, but mainly towards small initiatives. Guiding towards volumes and results (decrease of emissions) was lacking. Interaction at national level in some countries is minimal.
- High level discussions and negotiations only address directions, high targets and measures.
- There is no common story. People live in bubbles. Science is not debating with other partners of the quadruple helix. There is a lack of communication.
- NGO’s have only narrow ranges of interest.
- The scope of discussions is getting broader and a focus change from bioeconomy to biodiversity was reported.

When discussing possible barriers for an increasing bioeconomy limitations mentioned were that besides a lack of awareness and knowledge of the concept, the term bioeconomy itself is composed of two not very attractive and/or confusing words (bio+economy) and that bioeconomy products are not always the best option, which leads to lack of arguments. Little funding for dissemination of existing bioeconomy projects and missing training or curriculum on bioeconomy were other difficulties mentioned for a broader awareness of the bioeconomy. The profile of each territory was reported as decisive for the dissemination of the concept of bioeconomy (Spain).

Also Stakeholders in Finland missed more information about the source of the raw material, clear recycling options/information, information about used derivatives and transparency in the whole production chain.

In the Polish hub the participants were highlighting, that the society might not be ready, that there is a low trust level and a low cooperation level within the society. Financial, organisational and institutional issues were mentioned as barriers.

Swedish stakeholders expressed needs towards such as to learn more about sustainability and origin of materials but also predictability and structure.

In Austria the increasing commercialisation of nature, which may cause conflicts in how resources are distributed across society, heightened emissions through the possible reduction of carbon sinks (i.e. forests) or accelerated biodiversity loss. It was further feared that the benefits of the bioeconomy are reaped mainly by big industry rather than allowing for a deep-seated socio-ecological transformation.

The discussion on challenges and obstacles in Germany focused on the 'living standards' of consumers and the need to create a new understanding of nature. Further challenges and obstacles mentioned were the possible land requirements for a modified and expanded production of biological raw materials, which also exposed the conflict areas 'conservation of biodiversity' or '(investments in) innovations in harvesting technology'. Greenwashing has also been named as a possible challenge. In addition, the role of the media was discussed, esp. the question of who provides the information. They understood the at times negative (media) attention and a lack of education as the biggest barriers to bioeconomy. While the concept of bioeconomy itself is not a familiar concept in society, the debates, crises and conflicts in that field are well on the agenda.

Another aspect reported from Spain for the further co-creation process itself – and thus for future communication to and engagement with stakeholders in general - was that stakeholders try to preserve all the time differences in their status (researcher - technicians - public administration). It might happen that the group is not used to work participative on an even eye level or due to cultural reasons and being a bit less open to creative methods, the co-creation process people were a bit reserved to participate in rather experimental methods to co-create content.

4. BLOOM Hub-learnings when conveying the concept of bioeconomy

Bioeconomy is an income source, a chance for projects. As to potentials the participants in the hub workshops saw almost no boundaries. Mostly the emerging businesses and the potential for enhancing business with sustainable solutions were recognized. It was, however, important to stakeholders to also include critical points of view in the discussion. Suggestions for the following co-creation processes were made, such as

- Defining the concept, clarifying what bioeconomy is about and approaching society from the potentials of the bioeconomy with clear and concise messages, using success stories and tangible examples (from D1.1, D1.3.).

- Differentiating between bioeconomy products to facilitate their commercialisation and extension by companies and consumer knowledge (label, certificate, etcetera).
- Provide school applicable information.
- Raise awareness about sustainability work in the public sector, for example, by introducing bioeconomy as evaluation criteria in public procurement

It was clearly stated by hub partners, their stakeholders and the interviewees that for the bioeconomy to reach its full potential activities and measures should be taken that:

- develop educational material about bio-based products to inform citizens, in particular young people;
- support new bio-based industries and the greening of traditional industries;
- generate or reinforce informative and easily accessible online resources and online portals where information can be exchanged.

4.1. BLOOM's learnings on co-creation

Co-creation processes were at the heart of BLOOM's five regional hub activities because co-creation follows an approach of involving different perspectives and collaboratively designs tools, materials, processes, activities or strategies. A variety of targeted creative methods and creative tools feed into a guideline on engagement and co-creation (Deliverable D3.3) which supported the hub leaders in designing the most suitable workshops and to choose the most appropriate methodologies to communicate BLOOM's key messages. BLOOMs hubs launched co-creation workshops and local collaboration activities that assisted in better understanding the needs, barriers and existing (regional) knowledge gaps that have to be narrowed in order for a dynamic regional bioeconomy to flourish.

The co-creation phase has contributed to strengthen regional networks. In this context the co-creation phase has helped to fill those gaps that the bioeconomy clusters and the initiatives promoted by the regional strategies couldn't reach. The co-creation process has allowed to create an informal space where the participants can work together and think about the real needs of promoting the bioeconomy to the general public and offered excellent platform to extend the collaboration to young people who were identified as key stakeholder group in co-creation process. Especially, the co-creation approach led to a strengthening of existing regional networks and reached out beyond the hubs' initial regions.

The co-creation contributed to a lot of stakeholders from different sectors of society getting together for the first time and understanding the importance of communication and of citizen involvement for the transition and implementation of bioeconomy.

Co-creation enabled the identification of relevant and important target groups and dedicated outreach models. The hubs reported that the conducted outreach activities have contributed to reach out to more people from the academic sector, raising their interest in working on this sector.

BLOOM provided recommendations for modes of regional collaboration and network management bridging the identified barriers and gaps. Working in the hub co-creation teams allowed considering regional regulations, frames and funding schemes and infrastructure for an optimal research and innovation performance within the region and sought for an alignment of research

programs to the regional innovation strategy; from single disciplines to transdisciplinary knowledge and innovation.

4.2. BLOOM's learnings on outreach activities

The outreach and dissemination activities have raised wide interest among CSO, NGO and the general public. Young people (high school students), vocational school staff, high school staff contacted the hubs with requests for information or the wish to collaborate in dissemination and outreach activities.

Hubs' stakeholders have committed themselves to different outreach activities, because they shared the value of communicating the perspectives of bioeconomy and biobased innovations.

The general public to which open outreach activities were addressed, reacted positively and with great openness. It was observed that the focus of the hub on "innovative circular materials" and the BLOOM methods of bringing this focus closer to the people, increases the interest of the general public and civil society. Especially `showcases` and real-life examples make bioeconomy and BLOOM tangible.

Because of the Corona crisis, the hubs were thrown back on many online events. Although these formats were well applicable and could reach many people - far beyond national borders - but at the same time the "broad" public was lost, who were normally met at the planned (and previously also carried out) f2f events.

5. A look into the future

In general, a raising interest for bioeconomy and a Circular Bio-Economy was stated, because there's an increasing need to replace fossil raw materials. Openness for interactions between professionals and the general public is still a problem, the opportunity of co-creation is often not recognised, especially in stakeholder groups applying for similar funding. In general, there is a big interest in participation but difficulties to take the step to become active still remain. From the hubs experiences², practitioners' comments and experts' interviews the following topics and recommendations were given:

5.1. On governance

- Build awareness raising and outreach activities on a common understanding of an economic stable ecological society.
- Increase communication and outreach (bioeconomy standards, safety aspects, labels and certification, others) and overcome communication barriers between political parties.
- Organise more coordinated meetings between local/national policy makers and researchers to overcome the lack of communication
- Labelling and certification are necessary when addressing the global market with economic stable, well priced basic products, but to get there it needs a global concept for the dif-

² Details in project deliverables D1.1, 3.1, 3.2, 3.5, 4.1, 6.1

ferent value chains. The EU should push the need for certification and make it obligatory to receive grants.

- Bioeconomy on the lab scale is well established for processes to substitute fossil resources. But it needs support (investments, innovation policies) to upscale the processes and production to higher TRL.
- Establish an intermediate, independent association to give advice to stakeholders and make the voice of the public gets more heard.
- Listen to concerns of environmental groups.
- Foster regional approaches and interregional exchange on bioeconomy strategies, e.g. on availability of feedstock; infrastructure; access to finance; skilled workforce, technical expertise and training; strength and availability of regional markets; entrepreneurship; and public support policies.

5.2. On education

- Sustainability should be taught early on all educational paths. In schools and even in day-care, tomorrow's consumers could be introduced to responsible consumption.
- Bioeconomy should find also its way into 'everyday' teaching. Teaching should include information about new jobs as companies ask for new and different skills, scout for new materials and innovative solutions.
- Actions need to be done to further show the importance of Circular Sustainable Bioeconomy by including the topic in classrooms with actions that support the current curricula.
- Provide good teaching materials classes (video animations, visuals, games, quizzes...) in the respective language
- Underlay information with hands on experience. Field trips and seeing things with one's own eyes are useful to motivate people and to gain a better understanding of specific issues.
- Implement a system to rent out touchable bioeconomy products to schools
- Connect teachers and help them establishing networks and connect with other countries (e.g. via Erasmus), to increase the knowledge base on interdisciplinary teaching, to exchange students, to visit schools and companies and to get new ideas. This learning from other countries should also be considered by researchers as well as by policy makers.

5.3. For business and industry

- Companies have a quite narrow idea and understanding of their business. They need to open their eyes for new concepts.
- Overcome small scale initiatives. Interaction should be organised at the level of regions, but scale needs biomass availability. Build inter-regional value chains.
- Reach out more to the general public because at the moment 'value chain' is understood like a line, but instead the concept of clusters is very important.
- Consumers are important players and actors within the value chains. Behavioural change is needed to boost new consumption patterns.

5.4. On communication and outreach

- Embed any awareness raising activities into the national context
- Address the different stages in the implementation of bioeconomy strategies on European level, as well as the different approaches, definitions, interests and barriers
- Ensure exchange between projects working on similar problems and issues
- Adapt to existing communication and engagement structures in order to foster engagement of stakeholders
- Consider mind-set and mentality of your audience to motivate, fascinate and convince them to act.
- Consider the later commitment level - what types of participation are possible, conceivable, desirable.
- Use a variety of communication measures, forms and channels to create a climate of trust and shared values. Provide technical skills for staff and audience when using online tools
- Set up an internal communication strategy within the co-creation team (engaged stakeholders) that includes a mixture of different communication channels (digital, face-to-face) and the right intensity of communication (considering the time resources of all actors).
- Empower scientists so that they can communicate scientific, policy and business knowledge in a way that community partners can understand it and see the use for their own issues.
- Start by getting information about problems community is facing before applying for funding and starting actions on Community-academia partnerships
- Find a well-balanced mixture of face-to-face communication and online communication with the participating stakeholders.
- Be clear in the communication on responsibilities and expectations. Communicate clearly objectives to all stakeholders and partners.
- Provide usable guidelines to transfer dialogue results into action plans. Any kind of recommendations for action shall include a special focus on non-academic / educational target groups - how can they be encouraged / empowered / involved.

5.5. On co-creation

- Develop of a joint big vision and ensure reflexivity and a long term perspective
- Create confidence in the scientific background of the topic, but the difference between experts and non-experts has to be taken into account.
- Set a focus on policy if there is no already existing policy, set it on implementation if there is already one.
- Don't see participation only as top-down involvement in bioeconomy awareness raising. Participation should be seen as support to knowledge transfer, allowing to integrate freedom of research and bottom-up commitment.

- Include citizens in the planning process, also in selecting the co-creation format.
- Chose a bottom-up approach and conflict-sensitive adaptation, with a broad diversity of actors to develop new collaborations.
- As co-creation initiators find a way to shift the awareness of the participants about a certain issue into the willingness to act on it.
- Involve external facilitators/mediators to ensure the multi-directional knowledge transfer and overcome the gap between theory and reality
- Appreciate good ideas and integrate results of dialogues into follow up actions
- Try-out different co-creation methodologies to demonstrate that co-creation can be a mean of tackling bioeconomy awareness.
- Provide capacity building on co-creation methodologies, include intervention points and consider enough time for the preparation of participatory activities (online requests more preparation time). Also include joint hands-on activity to support “horizontality” between all stakeholders.
- Accept that there is no one best way to co-create: The implementation depends on countries and the relation between government, academia, business and citizens

6. A last word from the BLOOM hubs

This chapter adds to the summarised reflections and recommendations above that stem from the experiences the BLOOM hubs have made during the implementation of their activities. These outcomes and experiences are also represented in deliverable D3.5 – Report on activities.

Many of the hubs have worked to establish a local or regional network that even after the end of the BLOOM project knows how to engage with the general public on bioeconomic issues. In Spain, for example, the focus group has established a sustainable way of working together and the newsletter on bioeconomy will continue to be published after the project ending. In Sweden, for example, the goal in this project was to inspire the different stakeholders to make their own outreach activities. In Poland UAK is planning an educational project at the MA level concerning bioeconomy, which will use the experience of BLOOM. Another example is the bioeconomy suitcase/sample case with biobased product samples – available for and from all hubs - that will be available to rent after the project.

Around half of the outreach activities of the hubs have taken place during the Covid-19 pandemic. Therefore, a high level of flexibility was needed from all, hub team, co-creation team and stakeholders. When organizing a webinar instead of a personal event, several other aspects needed to be considered such as the number of inputs and enough room and time for discussion and interaction with the participants. The outreach activities that could be held as face to face events were very successful because of the interaction of quadruple helix partners and networking possibilities. Online formats cannot compete in this respect. The personal contacts and the individual engagement were crucial for the setup of all activities. This was even reinforced by the Corona crisis. All activities more or less were built on face to face contacts established before the lockdown.

The German co-hub experienced, when inviting for BLOOM activities, that the field of bioeconomy activities and projects is highly competitive in their region. Stakeholders saw time constraints

because of being asked to participate in many other projects' activities. Projects or other project teams were not cooperative in sharing thoughts in the beginning. Nevertheless, personal contacts, e.g. through participating in other projects' events (before Covid 19) or phone calls, created a level of trust among the hub team and stakeholders.

There's a large interest in acting more sustainable among the general public. But there's a lack of knowledge of how to do this and of already existing, materials, processes and new innovations, cutting-edge research. The importance of a being a "neutral" platform for bioeconomy related questions, not a marketplace but a dialogue space, was not only highlighted by the Nordic hub. Thus findings of other hubs were seen as important to share and discuss among the project partners.

Recommendation for future projects³

The **Spanish hub** recommends to:

- implement bottom-up co-creation processes. They are crucial in order to design effective activities
- always work with the educational sector: i.e. teachers and students. This forms the basis raise awareness of any topic

The **Polish hub** recommends to:

- build awareness of the term itself and what bioeconomy means. So a higher presence of this phrase in public space is desirable in any form.

The **Nordic hub** recommends to:

- initiate and foster knowledge exchange and collaboration between different bioeconomy projects and networks to avoid reinventing the wheel.

The **Dutch hub** recommends to:

- store the BLOOM materials and the concepts, and promote the use among EU, national and regional networks. The materials are very professional and can easily be re-used many more times in different public events.

The **Austrian and German** hub recommends to:

- show tangible examples of biobased products, as well as success stories, innovations

Even though the BLOOM project has now ended and the hubs as such no longer exist, the partners in the established networks will continue to cooperate and further contribute to an awareness raising on circular sustainable bioeconomy.

³ The full list can be read in Deliverable D3.5

7. References

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